

Conflict Resolution of Social Assistance Distribution during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract: *The Covid-19 pandemic as a non-natural disaster has an impact on the stability and conduciveness of people's lives. Various economic and social impacts caused result in their lives being threatened. The central government and local governments as public servants are expected to be able to assist the community, especially those affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. This social assistance program created by the ministry of social affairs turned out to cause conflicts in the implementation of social assistance distribution. The distribution of social assistance carried out in the community is considered not on target, causing disappointment for the injustice they feel. Therefore, the government is required to be able to resolve the conflict that occurred by making strategic steps starting with conducting an assessment and analysis of the causes, impacts and solutions taken in resolving social assistance distribution conflicts during the Covid-19 pandemic.*

Keywords : *Conflict Resolution, Distribution of Social Assistance, The Covid-19 Pandemic.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Human in his status as a social being is certainly inseparable from the plurality of a conflict. Conflict itself is a social fact that is always related to activities or activities in the lives of individuals and groups. At the end of 2019, all parts of the world are experiencing an electrifying event with a finding of the Covid-19 pandemic outbreak or known as the Corona Virus. The pandemic is known as an epidemic that then spreads to several other regions since the first findings in a region. It is known that this virus originated in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, China (Yuliana, 2020). On March 12, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) announced Covid-19 as a pandemic. While in Indonesia, Covid-19 is recognized to have entered since the end of January 2020 (Kumparan, 2020).

In terms of handling and preventing the spread of Covid-19 in Indonesia, the government has made strategic policies contained in the legal umbrella. Among them is the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 of 2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters for the Spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) as a national disaster, Regulation of the Minister of Health Number 9 of 2020 concerning PSBB guidelines for areas categorized as red zones, Circular Letter of the Ministry of Education Number 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of Education in the emergency period of the Covid-19 pandemic (Arifin in Fathimah, 2020).

A pandemic is an unexpected situation and condition. The changes that occur not only have an impact on the health sector but have an impact on other sectors such as the economy which is significant to the welfare of the community. The Covid-19 pandemic requires the enactment of large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) in Indonesia in general and especially in some areas categorized in the Covid-19 red zone. In implication, the

enactment of this PSBB resulted in economic movements being hampered and the cycle becoming messy. For example, people who are no longer free to travel, job cuts (layoffs), and so on (Herdiana, 2020).

Empirically, the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic is felt by all levels of society, but especially people who are classified as middle to lower, because the majority of them are workers in the informal sector who depend on daily wages. With the enactment of rules on policies from the government on activities that can only be done at home, ranging from working at home to even the teaching and learning process that can only be done at home also suppresses the decline in community welfare which affects all communities. Problems like this if allowed to drag on will result in increased poverty rates and eliminate livelihoods for the lower middle class in their survival in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic (Mufida, 2020).

The government as a public servant also responded to this situation by making efforts to deal with economic setbacks felt by the community. The action carried out by the government began with the determination of policies in the form of regulations governing the financial policies of countries and regions during the pandemic. In addition, the central government and local governments also took action to provide social assistance to communities affected by the pandemic as a measure to deal with the Covid-19 virus pandemic (Fathimah, 2020). With the government's involvement in a policy of providing social assistance, it is hoped that it can help people who are experiencing difficulties during the Covid-19 pandemic. The government in its concern for citizens or communities is not only because of the pandemic but has become one of its roles as a servant of the state. In the occurrence of natural and non-natural disasters, both local and central governments are often found distributing social assistance to the community.

In its implementation, the government is often considered less than optimal by the community as a recipient of assistance and even the community feels disappointed by the inequality and injustice committed by the government. The government in its duty to serve the community, especially in the implementation of social assistance programs affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, has not been maximally implemented by the mutually agreed goals (Fathimah, 2020). As for some of the problems found in its implementation such as assisting inappropriate target recipients, community data is categorized in classification based on the level of poverty that is not appropriate, the provision of social assistance that is slow to be received, thus impacting injustice and so on (Rahmansyah, 2020).

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the government in its policy provided a variety of social assistance provided to affected communities. Some of these assistance include Presidential Social Assistance, Provincial Social Assistance, Regency / City Social Assistance, and even assistance sourced from Village Funds. In some regions in Indonesia, there are similar problems in the distribution of social assistance, one of which is the province of West Java (Fathimah, 2020). West Java Province, led by Ridwan Kamil, found a mismatch in the data of the recipient community so that the target recipients of assistance were those who received double assistance and people who should not be registered but instead registered. For example, residents who have been registered as recipients of assistance by provincial social assistance but are still registered as recipients of district/city assistance or registered as recipients of the Beneficiary Family program (KPM), Family Hope Program (PKH), and other assistance or programs (CNN, 2020).

II. DISCUSSION

Problems arising from the plurality of the situation during this pandemic encouraged efforts to handle it from the government. The government responds directly to this situation with a real impact on people's lives, especially the poor, most of whom have lost their jobs because their income sources are restricted or prohibited from operating on the grounds of suppressing the rate of spread of Covid-19. In its handling, the government took

various preventive measures where the Ministry of Social Affairs as the spearhead of the government was given authority and power in handling the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. By continuing to coordinate with cross-sectors and supported by rules as a legal basis as well as norms and resources. Responding to this, the Ministry of Social Affairs then made a policy in the form of a community social assistance program for all citizens affected by the Covid-19 pandemic (Fathimah, 2020).

The socio-economic life of the people affected by the Covid-19 pandemic has implications for the poverty rate to increase with the unemployment index rising by about 3.78 million people and 5.2 million people who have experienced job cuts (Tambun, 2020). On this basis, the socio-economic sector is one of the sectors most affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. For this reason, the government is expected to provide solutions to this problem, especially for the welfare of the affected communities. In its implementation, the Ministry of Social Affairs, under its authority, provides social assistance to the community in the form of food raw materials to the community to survive amid the plurality of the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. However, over time during the pandemic, there was also a conflict over social assistance between the government and the community.

Conflicts that occur are caused by several fundamental factors such as abuse of authority and power and factors in the field. As a spearhead in the social aspects of the impact of the pandemic, it is certainly not easy for the Ministry of Social Affairs to perform its role so there is a need for coordination, supervision, and evaluation. The discussion of the conflict of distribution of social assistance can be seen in horizontal and vertical forms. Horizontal conflict refers to conflicts between people arising from the disorderly distribution of social assistance as well as the result of disputes themselves (Fathimah, 2020). While vertical conflict is a conflict that occurs between the government and the community caused by the policies made and the implementation of the policy.

In the implementation of the distribution of social assistance, both by the central and local governments, in general, become a source of conflict that refers to the distribution of social assistance that is not on target or uneven for justice. The assistance provided in numbers has a nominal that is different from each region and between types of assistance from one to another, so this is very vulnerable to triggering conflict. Then, with the many types of assistance provided by the government both the central and local governments, as a result, caused overlap (Fathimah, 2020).

This problem causes the local government as a distributor to be confused so that there are people who have received assistance A while there are also those who receive assistance B with unequal values. This certainly causes a sense of injustice and social jealousy in the communities affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. In addition, on the other hand, there is an act of abuse of authority that results in social assistance provided to the community being already in an inappropriate condition (Sindonews, 2020). Then, during the escalating pandemic situation, there is a problem that becomes a new conflict, namely, there are several government officials who are examined by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK), one of which is the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, namely Juliari P Batubara, who is related to the case of social assistance bribery (Tribunnews, 2020).

In carrying out an act of resolving a conflict, of course, there must be a review and analysis of the cause of the problem and the impact and strategic ways that can be taken and done in resolving existing conflicts and problems. Therefore, what can be done in solving problems related to the problem of social assistance distribution is of them started by the central and local governments to carry out the preparation of regulatory or regulatory formulations that become the basis of every action taken (Herdina, 2020).

In carrying out conflict resolution actions, the main thing is to make a strategic ledge in conflict resolution. The Ministry of Social Affairs through social services is expected to be able to coordinate and synergize with cross-sectors in conflict resolution, especially regarding the conformity of data on people affected by the Covid-19

pandemic. In conducting data collection, the government must be selective in recording people who are entitled to receive based on the conditions met as recipients of social assistance. Then, the government must actively update the data by recording and field surveys to obtain the appropriate data. In addition, it is also necessary to appeal to the public to report to the government if any of their family members have died or moved domiciles or residences so as not to affect the validity of the data made in the distribution of social assistance. Then in providing social assistance, it is expected that in accordance with the applicable law so that the distribution of social assistance due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic can be in accordance with the expected goals of both the government and the community (Fachrudin, 2004).

Social assistance policies and other policies in handling conflicts during the Covid-19 pandemic made by the central government and local governments must be monitored both internally and externally (Herdiana, 2020). This is based on a reason that validates that the government as a state organization that is given duties and responsibilities in the implementation of government must be carried out effectively and efficiently. And based on the rule of law and regulation. Supervision is an important thing and needs to be done in a multi-actor manner both internally and externally ranging from the central government, and local government to the village/village level. As for also from supervisory institutions such as the Audit Board, the Corruption Enforcement Commission and non-governmental institutions and the community itself in a value will pay attention to the successful distribution of social assistance.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 pandemic has greatly impacted the stability of Indonesian people's lives. The problems caused are very diverse and complex. The government as a public servant is expected to be able to provide social assistance for the community during the Covid-19 pandemic situation. The implementation of this social assistance program is considered not on target and becomes a new conflict in the community that feels the economic and social impacts of the Covid19 pandemic. This certainly causes disappointment and pain for the community towards the government because of their rights that have not been as expected. Therefore, the government is required to be able to carry out its duties and functions as well as possible by conducting conflict resolution, especially regarding the distribution of social assistance.

In solving problems, the government first conducts a review and analysis of the causes, as well as the impact and appropriate solutions in the implementation of social assistance distribution. In addition, in resolving conflicts, the government coordinates and synergizes with cross-sectors to get strategic and targeted steps so that existing conflicts can be resolved immediately. In its implementation, the step taken is to make mapping with the preparation of parties involved in conflict resolution efforts which in this case social services as an extension of the social ministry. Furthermore, resolving conflicts is also based on mediation, contact, and efforts to build trust as a form of government responsibility to the community in general and especially those affected by the Covid-19 pandemic.

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